

MIMS 4.21-22 - White and Black Spaces in Meditation

Where MIMS 4.2 is meditation¹

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ABSTRACT

Both the author and patients of the author's, as well as others in the lexicon of meditation, report experiencing black spaces and white spaces (bright lights), where they feel strong senses of different modes of consciousness, emotion, and/or changed perceptions of time. Are these spaces connected to the various fibonacci sequence structures, chiefly the Void and Aether, respectively? If so, what are the mimsical implications of these altered states of consciousness, and might they provide tangible, material benefits that can be measured, and indicate some level of extractable worth from an essentially free practice? What hypotheses can be gleaned from a short discussion about these experiences?

Key Words: MIMS - meditation - profit - void - vacuum - 0 point - aether - free energy - wealth - mind

¹ While the author has previously discussed prayer as a MIMS [4.1], meditation has not been overtly discussed.

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Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

MIMS 4.2 - Meditation as an interface with the Divine	3
Table 1 - Taoism and Meditation's Importance	6
MIMS 4.21 - Encountering the Black Space	9
MIMS 4.22 - Encountering the White Space	11
Hypotheses and Conclusions	13
References	14

MIMS 4.2 - Meditation as an interface with the Divine

The author has full authority to retcon prayer into MIMS 4.1 and in similar fashion to retcon a non-EPEMC paper into EPEMC via MIMS 4.2. MED 2.01 will cover the medical aspects and benefits of meditation, and bring the concept of Qi as a scalar [electro]magnetic wave² into the EPEMC umbrella.

Suffice it to say the author *knows and can prove* that meditation has a positive effect on one's material life, and many studies show the benefits of various forms of meditation:

- EMDR³
- MBM^{4 5 6} / MBSR⁷
- Biofeedback⁸
- Induced trance⁹
- Transcendental Meditation¹⁰
- Psychedelic related trance¹¹
- Yoga
- Qigong
- Hypnosis¹²

The positive benefits outweigh, statistically, the negative, of which there are many, and those will be covered mostly in MIMS 2.2.1.1-3.¹³ However, the fact remains that all of the spiritual texts maintain that God/"the Lord" wants you to be benefited, and despite all approbations or worries of the disconnected rabble who huddle into churches and temples saying otherwise, He wants a *direct* connection. This is proven by none other than Yeshua's (Jesus') own sayings:

- ❖ *"Behold, I stand at the door and knock. If anyone hears my voice and opens the door, I will come in to him and eat with him, and he with me."*¹⁴
- ❖ *"For I know the plans I have for you, declares the Lord, plans for welfare and not for evil, to give you a future and a hope."*¹⁵
- ❖ *"Jesus said to him, "I am the way, and the truth, and the life. No one comes to the Father except through me."*¹⁶

² https://www.academia.edu/8547496/Scalar_Magnetic_Waves_and_Qi_a_first_draft_of_a_hypothesis

³ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29018388/>

⁴ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3679190/>

⁵ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6597263/>

⁶ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32406348/>

⁷ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22805898/>

⁸ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/6986134/>

⁹ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/336648/>

¹⁰ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18854202/>

¹¹ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32931403/>

¹² Insofar as it is an altered state of consciousness without ego or intellectual interference.

¹³ <https://bit.ly/3lsecCl>

¹⁴ Revelation 3:20

¹⁵ Jeremiah 29:11

¹⁶ John 14:6

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- ❖ *“I am the vine; you are the branches. Whoever abides in me and I in him, he it is that bears much fruit, for apart from me you can do nothing.”¹⁷*
- ❖ *“But he gives more grace. Therefore it says, “God opposes the proud, but gives grace to the humble.” Submit yourselves therefore to God. Resist the devil, and he will flee from you. Draw near to God, and he will draw near to you. Cleanse your hands, you sinners, and purify your hearts, you double-minded. Be wretched and mourn and weep. Let your laughter be turned to mourning and your joy to gloom. Humble yourselves before the Lord, and he will exalt you.”¹⁸*
- ❖ *“Jesus answered him, “If anyone loves me, he will keep my word, and my Father will love him, and we will come to him and make our home with him.”¹⁹*
- ❖ *“Jesus answered him, “Truly, truly, I say to you, unless one is born again he cannot see the kingdom of God.”²⁰*

And for the Gnostics:

“(2) Jesus says:

- (1) “The one who seeks should not cease seeking until he finds.*
- (2) And when he finds, he will be dismayed.*
- (3) And when he is dismayed, he will be astonished.*
- (4) And he will be king over the All.”*

(3) Jesus says:

- (1) “If those who lead you say to you: ‘Look, the kingdom is in the sky!’ then the birds of the sky will precede you.*
- (2) If they say to you: ‘It is in the sea,’ then the fishes will precede you.*
- (3) Rather, the kingdom is inside of you and outside of you.”*
- (4) “When you come to know yourselves, then you will be known, and you will realize that you are the children of the living Father.*
- (5) But if you do not come to know yourselves, then you exist in poverty, and you are poverty.*

(10) Jesus says: “I have cast fire upon the world, and see, I am guarding it until it blazes.”²¹

Why does God want this connection? What is the natural benefit of it? It is one thing to “ask and ye shall receive, knock and it will be answered.”²² It is another thing to connect directly, as if on a network of birkeland currents, and then knock and have direct connection. There is

¹⁷ John 15:5

¹⁸ James 4:6-10

¹⁹ John 14:23

²⁰ John 3:3

²¹ Book of Thomas

<https://www.biblicalarchaeology.org/daily/biblical-topics/bible-versions-and-translations/the-gospel-of-thomas-114-sayings-of-jesus/>

²² Matthew 7:7-8 “7 Ask, and it shall be given you; seek, and ye shall find; knock, and it shall be opened unto you:

8 For every one that asketh receiveth; and he that seeketh findeth; and to him that knocketh it shall be opened.”

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Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

some indication, as discussed in the aforementioned paper with regard to the heart-mind connection, that there is a real, and tangible interface (a pinging, to borrow the old DOS term) occurring and that it is not “all in your head.” This is supported both by macro-studies, as covered by G. Hancock²³, et al. and in the author’s own work with signals²⁴ and Charge Distributive Network²⁵ circuit design and accompanying in clinic (in situ) electromagnetic field measurements.²⁶


```
C:\WINDOWS\system32\cmd.exe
Microsoft Windows [Version 10.0.19043.1415]
(c) Microsoft Corporation. All rights reserved.

C:\Users\16194>ping www.google.com

Pinging www.google.com [142.250.177.36] with 32 bytes of data:
Reply from 142.250.177.36: bytes=32 time=20ms TTL=120
Reply from 142.250.177.36: bytes=32 time=19ms TTL=120
Reply from 142.250.177.36: bytes=32 time=19ms TTL=120
Reply from 142.250.177.36: bytes=32 time=20ms TTL=120

Ping statistics for 142.250.177.36:
    Packets: Sent = 4, Received = 4, Lost = 0 (0% loss),
    Approximate round trip times in milli-seconds:
        Minimum = 19ms, Maximum = 20ms, Average = 19ms

C:\Users\16194>ping God
Ping request could not find host God. Please check the name and try again.

C:\Users\16194>_
```

Figure 1 - “run cmd”; credit: Microsoft/author²⁷

Setting aside the brain as a transceiver concept, there is also the point G. Hancock makes about the “junk DNA” in our cells following Zipf’s Law.²⁸ What would this mean, if the MED 2.01 paper is right about (a) scalar waves (Meyl/Careaga), and (b) the DNA acting as a particle accelerating multi-phase, multi-tone, multi-amplifying, multi-mode-attenuating transformer (MPTMAMAT or “empty MamaT” for short)²⁹?

²³ <https://www.amazon.com/Supernatural-Meetings-Ancient-Teachers-Mankind/dp/1932857842>

²⁴ <https://bit.ly/3r2Qor1>

²⁵

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330117614_Charge_Distribution_Networks_CDN_as_Meridians_Utilizing_conductivity_as_replacement_%27structure%27_for_meridians_comparison_with_neural_muscular_and_fascial_models

²⁶

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328697566_Clinical_Electric_Field_Measurements_In_situ_pre_and_post_treatment_measurement_data_with_weather_and_space-weather_lunar_and_solar_data_with_self-reported_pain_and_significance_scales_in_three_phases

²⁷ The fact that we cannot connect yet to host God means we have a lot of work to do, and in fact may already be losing a certain battle (for our souls?). But mostly the author finds it funny to make Microsoft/Bill Gates admit it cannot find God. :)

²⁸ <https://www.britannica.com/science/information-theory/Linguistics>

²⁹ Clarage/Thornhill/Tennant/Careaga/Samuel ; sources: various

Figure 2 - Empty Mama-T pities our society; credit: author/MHSABA³⁰

All jokes aside, the use of meditation is probably *understated* here, if anything, rather than overstated. In the acquisition of material happiness, the elimination of the desire and attachment to material happiness has been one of the most consistent themes and products of meditation and meditation-based cultures.

To iron in the point, let us quote from three Taoist texts, all of which are the author's favorites. But bear in mind, Zhuangzi (Chuang Tsu)³¹ and Liezi (Lieh Tzu)³² also talked about it extensively, as well as of course a plethora of Buddhist and Hindu sutras (suttas).

Table 1 - Taoism and Meditation's Importance

<i>Nei Yeh</i> ³³	<i>Tao Te Ch'ing (Daodejing)</i> ³⁴	<i>Hua Hu Ch'ing (Huahujing)</i> ³⁵
<p>This vital energy (Qi) Cannot be halted by force, Yet can be secured by inner power (Te). When inner power develops and wisdom emerges, The myriad things will, to the last one, be grasped. The Way has no fixed position; It abides within the excellent mind. When the mind is tranquil and the vital breath is regular, The Way can thereby be halted. Cultivate your mind, make</p>	<p>The five colours blind the eyes of men. The five tones deafen their ears. The five flavours vitiate their palates. Galloping and hunting induce derangement of the mind. Objects that are difficult of attainment lead them to incur obstacles, [or injury—in their pursuit]. Thus the Sage cares for his inner self, and not for that which his eye can see; for which reason he discards the latter and preserves the</p>	<p>Men and women who wish to be aware of the whole truth should adopt the practices of the Integral Way. These time-honored disciplines calm the mind and bring one into harmony with all things. The first practice is the practice of indiscriminating virtue: take care of those who are deserving; also, and equally, take care of those who are not. When you extend your virtue in all directions without discriminating, your feet are firmly planted on the path that returns to the Tao. Do you imagine the universe</p>

³⁰ <https://theme-me.com/2013/05/21/day-328-mr-t-a-team-costume/mr-t-costume-mid-kiss-fists/>

³¹ <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Zhuangzi>

³² <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Liezi-Daoist-philosopher>

³³ <https://www.amazon.com/Original-Tao-Foundations-Mysticism-Translations/dp/0231115652>

³⁴ <https://www.sacred-texts.com/tao/taote.htm>

³⁵ <https://www.amazon.com/Hua-Hu-Ching-Teachings-Lao/dp/0060692456>

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your thoughts tranquil,
And the Way can thereby be
attained.
As for the Way:
When people lose it they die;
When people gain it they
flourish. When endeavors
lose it they fail; When they
gain it they succeed.
The vital essence: it is the
essence of the vital energy.
When the vital energy is
guided, it [the vital essence]
is generated, But when it is
generated, there is thought,
When there is thought, there
is knowledge, But when there
is knowledge, then you must
stop.
Or else you lose your vitality.
When your body is not
aligned, the inner power will
not come.
When you are not tranquil
within, your mind will not be
well ordered.
Align your body, assist the
inner power, then it will
gradually come on its own.
When you have no delusions
within you, externally there
will be no disasters.
Those who keep their minds
unimpaired within, externally
keep their bodies unimpaired,
Who do not encounter
heavenly disasters or meet
with harm at the hands of
others, call them Sages.
If people can be aligned and
tranquil, their skin will be
ample and smooth, their ears
and eyes will be acute and
clear, their muscles will be

former.
If one represses his lustful
inclinations and closes his
door, he will be in quietude
all his life: but if he gives
rein to voluptuousness and
indulges his desires, there
will never be any salvation
for him.
He who can perceive things
that are minute is called
clear-sighted. He who
hushes his weakness is
called resolute, or strong
minded. He who uses the
light that is in him will revert
to his native perspicacity.
Not exposing the body to
disaster implies the practice
of ethical morality.
When one feels a desire to
concentrate it [in one's own
heart], it is imperatively
necessary to display it
openly.
When one feels a desire to
cultivate it in its pliant phase,
it is imperatively necessary to
fortify and strengthen [one's
own powers].
When one feels a desire to
abandon or neglect it, it is
imperatively necessary to stir
up one's mind afresh [in its
pursuit].
If anyone feels a desire to
obtain it, it is imperatively
necessary that it should be
imparted to him.
By this means, the hidden
phases [of TAO] will become
clear. The weak and pliable
overcomes the strong and
hard.
Those who understand [the
TAO] are up conscious of

is agitated? Go into the desert
at night and look out at the
stars. This practice should
answer the question. The
superior person settles her
mind as the universe settles
the stars in the sky. By
connecting her mind with the
subtle origin, she calms it.
Once calmed, it naturally
expands, and ultimately her
mind becomes as vast and
immeasurable as the night
sky.
The Tao gives rise to all
forms, yet it has no form of its
own. If you attempt to fix a
picture of it in your mind, you
will lose it. This is like pinning
a butterfly: the husk is
captured, but the flying is lost.
Why not be content with
simply experiencing it?
I confess that there is nothing
to teach: no religion, no
science, no body of
information which will lead
your mind back to the Tao.
Today I speak in this fashion,
tomorrow in another, but
always the Integral Way is
beyond words and beyond
mind. Simply be aware of the
oneness of things.
Does one scent appeal more
than another? Do you prefer
this flavor, or that feeling? Is
your practice sacred and your
work profane? Then your
mind is separated: from itself,
from oneness, from the Tao.
Keep your mind free of
divisions and distinctions.
When your mind is detached,
simple, quiet, then all things
can exist in harmony, and you
can begin to perceive the
subtle truth.
The tiny particles which form
the vast universe are not tiny
at all. Neither is the vast

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Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

supple and their bones will be strong.

Reverently be aware of the Way and do not waver, and you will daily renew your inner power.

When there is a mind that is unimpaired within you, it cannot be hidden.

It will be known in your countenance, and seen in your skin color.

If with this good flow of vital energy you encounter others, They will be kinder to you than your own brethren.

This is because the wordless pronouncement is more rapid than the drumming of thunder.

Just let a balanced and aligned breathing fill your chest and it will swirl and blend within your mind, This confers longevity.

When joy and anger are not limited, you should make a plan to limit them.

Just let a balanced and aligned breathing fill your chest. When you enlarge your mind and let go of it, When you relax your vital breath and expand it, When your body is calm and unmoving: this is called "revolving the vital breath" Even your thoughts and deeds seem heavenly. The vitality of all people Inevitably comes from their peace of mind. When anxious, you lose this guiding thread; When angry, you lose

their upward progress. Those who count their ignorance as knowledge, are diseased. It is only those who treat themselves as sick who are therefore free from disease. The Sage, who is not diseased, treats himself as though he were; wherefore his disease becomes no disease at all.

He who, conscious of manly strength, guards a womanly weakness, becomes the channel of the whole Empire [to which all minor streams converge]. Being thus the channel of the whole Empire, the cardinal virtues will never depart from him, and he will revert to a condition of childlike innocence.

He who, conscious of light, keeps in obscurity, will become a model for the whole Empire. Being a model for the whole Empire, the cardinal virtues will never fail him, and he will revert to the Unconditioned.

He who, conscious of his glory, guards humility, will become the valley of the whole Empire. Being the valley of the Empire, he will revert to his original simplicity. When this simplicity is distributed, *q.d.*, brought into play, the man becomes a thing of utility [to the State].

The Sage employs men of

universe vast. These are notions of the mind, which is like a knife, always chipping away at the Tao, trying to render it graspable and manageable. But that which is beyond form is ungraspable, and that which is beyond knowing is unmanageable. There is, however, this consolation: She who lets go of the knife will find the Tao at her fingertips.

The clairvoyant may see forms which are elsewhere, but he cannot see the formless. The telepathic may communicate directly with the mind of another, but he cannot communicate with one who has achieved no-mind. The telekinetic may move an object without touching it, but he cannot move the intangible. Such abilities have meaning only in the realm of duality. Therefore, they are meaningless. Within the Great Oneness, though there is no such thing as clairvoyance, telepathy, or telekinesis, all things are seen, all things understood, all things forever in their proper places.

Each moment is fragile and fleeting. The moment of the past cannot be kept, however beautiful. The moment of the present cannot be held, however enjoyable. The moment of the future cannot be caught, however desirable. But the mind is desperate to fix the river in place: Possessed by ideas of the past, preoccupied with images of the future, it overlooks the plain truth of the moment. The one who can dissolve her mind will

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Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

this basic point.
When you are anxious or sad, pleased or angry, The Way has no place within you to settle. That mysterious vital energy within the mind: One moment it arrives, the next it departs.
For people who have attained the Way it permeates their pores and saturates their hair. Within their chest, they remain unvanquished. (sic)

this simplicity, and advances them to high rank; therefore his administration is on a grand scale, and never comes to an end. (sic)

suddenly discover the Tao at her feet, and clarity at hand. How can the divine Oneness be seen? In beautiful forms, breathtaking wonders, awe-inspiring miracles? The Tao is not obliged to present itself this way. It is always present and always available. When speech is exhausted and the mind dissolved, it presents itself. When clarity and purity are cultivated, it reveals itself. When sincerity is unconditional, it unveils itself. If you are willing to be lived by it, you will see it everywhere, even in the most ordinary things.

What matters is not that the individual buys into meditation, per se. Many people tell the author in the clinical setting that they “cannot relax” or “empty the mind” long enough, without losing interest. That’s so common that the author feels it is not likely a very good solution - as a MIMS - for 90+% of the general public. However, the author also remains factual that there isn’t much else that will provide an equivalent output. In terms of cost, setting aside time, it is **free**, and so if one divides the output in \$\$ or other material values turned into \$\$, and divides by this cost, the result is essentially infinite gain. Consider that, for the moment. Other than free air and water, is there a better deal? Not even love is as free!

MIMS 4.21 - Encountering the Black Space

When patients, and meditators, are new to the meditation, it is typical, almost a trope, that they encounter the black space. At first, of course they do not encounter this, but they see colors, images, random noise, “sparkly dots,” etc. Instead of empty bliss, the person is encountering their stress, active neurotransmitters, etc. due to chemistry and the sympathetic nervous system. Rather, they are not there yet because they are not connected to the Void directly.

It is very difficult to connect to the Void (or Counterspace), if that theoretically can even happen.

What would even be the benefit? When patients go into a deep, deep sleep on the table and are unresponsive to most noise (low wakefulness³⁶), even forgetting the time or even day upon waking, they are thought by Chinese Sciences to be traveling in spirit outside of their body.

³⁶ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2701283/>

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Could this be possible? Can an aetheric anatomy or body exist and could it separate and then float about, without the physical body dying³⁷?

It seems likely, based on the Law of Polarity³⁸, that an aetheric body is factual. In fact, it is the greatest in terms of available energy and knowledge. But the fact remains that we are low on evidence, not merely because the aether is only just now being found, but because there is a difficulty in photographing and videographing plasmoid “ghosts” in general. We are not really very sure what plasma balls are. We have scant footage, although the author can personally confirm the footage of one plasmoid, moving in a spiral as if running along a birkeland current!

Figure 3 - Plasma Ghost³⁹ “On Location”⁴⁰; credit: D. Hicks/K. Kauffman⁴¹

However, even with ball lightning the footage is scant, and there’s no proof that ball lightning itself is conscious orbs. In this case there was strong circumstantial evidence, as well as professional confirmation. But the use of low light mode on cameras is probably rare.

But let us suppose that the person’s spirit can leave their body, leaving the physical brain to immediately explore its own chemistry. Is there a connection between this “going into the Void” and the factual experience of truly seeing the Black Space? The author has no data, only personal experience. In fact the author has no proof, whatsoever, that the Black Space

³⁷ The Tibetans maintain that their death meditation allows the consciousness to remain in this domain, but in aetheric form, and the body does not decay. Their practices are secretive, however, and the author feels it is also due, potentially, to the consumption of oils and incense which are known to preserve the body. However, how is it that the body does not rot at all, or produce much smell? These corpses can remain intact for over a month’s time as confirmed by western medical doctors, whose typical explanation is that a chronic degenerative condition (like cancer) is staving off the death.

³⁸ Physical Body = yin; Aetheric Body = yang

³⁹ Please note the author is off to the left, off camera, and can confirm the room was present with extra energies, although the author cannot confirm it was a “ghost” per se as he doesn’t see apparitions.

⁴⁰ Wicked World Scare Grounds, Lexington, KY (2014)

⁴¹ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DJAmj1NxJ_w

experience is a mimsical one at all. What outcomes, positive and material, could there be? IS there any real or tangible proof that meditators that are experiencing high-performance lives also are truly experiencing the Black Space?

What the author proposes, is that although the answer is no, it could be tested with fMRI and data could be found, which would provide some type of confirmation. To do so would require the careful questioning from an experienced meditator to make sure the individual is not merely experiencing “Oblivion” and is truly touching the Void. There also should be non-fMRI physical signs, like increasing “onyx eyes” and a detached, personality-less response. An entire protocol would need to be developed by an MBMR psychologist or psychiatrist/researcher for study with a pre-cognitive evaluation and post-event cognitive evaluation acting as controls. Achieving the Black Space is a skill that improves with consistent practice, also, and this (as well as proposed material gains and losses⁴²) can and should be measured dutifully over several months to several years of study.

MIMS 4.22 - Encountering the White Space

Quite similarly, the author has also noticed that there appears to be a related experience, rarer in accomplishment at first, where the consciousness can encounter the Aether, so it seems, and experienced either an incredible bliss (rather than the empty nothingness and peace of the Black Space), as well as incredible energy. The energy can be so powerful, in fact, that the individual can feel a powerful current in the spine that causes an arching which enables a form of yoga that involves meditating between two chairs. For there, ostensibly, the individual can enter aetheric spaces, astral, “heavens” etc. and never notice the time shift, etc.

This invitation, also, is granted, and not only physiological, and this differentiates it from the Voidist experience. It is something that definitely confers new skills, and requires continual new skill and practice. It is, assuredly, a gong - shen gong - and takes a repeated effort and energy. It also may, according to Table 1 et al., require a certain mentality. Could this also be what enabled Yeshua his powers and patience to “pray”⁴³ for “40 days”⁴⁴ in the desert? Is this related to his experience of being tempted three times?⁴⁵ Siddhartha Gautama Buddha also reported being tempted.⁴⁶ And there are a number of so called “spirit blocks” which exist for meditators, according to Chinese Yoga⁴⁷:

- Oblivion⁴⁸
- Distraction
- 3 Corpses/Poisons⁴⁹
- 5 Worms⁵⁰

⁴² For it could also be an anti-MIMS as well.

⁴³ No one talks aloud for 40 days, not even zealots. But Ch’an/Zen is routinely done for extended periods of time.

⁴⁴ The argument has been made recently to the author that this is a euphemism for “a long time”.

⁴⁵ Matthew 4:1-11

⁴⁶ <https://www.learnreligions.com/the-demon-mara-449981>

⁴⁷ <https://www.amazon.com/Taoist-Yoga-Kuan-Charles-Luk/dp/0877280673>

⁴⁸ <https://terebess.hu/keletkultinfo/Cleary-Thomas-Secret-of-the-Golden-Flower.pdf>

⁴⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Three_Corpses

⁵⁰ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bigu_\(grain_avoidance\)#The_Three_Corpses_or_Worms](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bigu_(grain_avoidance)#The_Three_Corpses_or_Worms)

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- 7 depraved Po (bodily souls)⁵¹

The author also notes that there are the following clinical blocks, which exist beyond typical Chinese Medicine blocks like wind, cold, damp, etc.⁵²:

- Thoughtforms (typically “hauntings” by memory, obsessions, other psychological schisms)
- Frequency jammings (mostly mental hang ups, again obsessions, some physical)
- Karmic (usually familial) limitors (such as physical defects, name issues, curses, including burdens from God⁵³, etc.)
- Addictions and thought-grooves (like “being in a rut”, or having a song repeat in one’s head all the time)
- Chemical limitations, mineralogical, pharmacological, dietary, etc.
- Etc.

These types of problems, which can cause or combine with mental and physical and psychosomatic pathologies, really can block the individual from achieving the types of results spoken of above.

But, again we need **data**, and the author must propose that a similar experiment like before be done. Or perhaps the same study with blinding that compares the two groups, as well as a prayer or other mimsical control group, perhaps people who read self-help books, etc. But however it is performed, by competent professionals and overseen by professionals and acceptable meditation experts, it must be clear:

- ★ Measure any and all material changes in their lives, monetary or otherwise (including relationships, sex, happiness, etc.), and map out the chronology carefully
 - Eliminate normal cyclic changes and normalcy like car issues, job pay, mortgages etc. (establish these sinusoids early on)
 - Don’t ignore some of those changes, however, they could be part of the mimsical experience.

⁵¹ “Chinese Medical Qigong Therapy: Vol. 2: Energetic Alchemy, Dao Yin Therapy and Qi Deviations,” P.J.A. Johnson, 2002 pp. 153-158

⁵² As per Huangdi Neijing Suwen;

http://www.biblio.nhat-nam.ru/Huang_Di_Nei_Jing_Su_Wen-Unschuld-Tessenow-1-2.pdf

⁵³ Exodus 34:7 & Number 14:18; see: https://www.openbible.info/topics/generational_curses

Hypotheses and Conclusions

1. That the Black space is the individual encountering the Counterspace/Void
2. That the individual's spirit body is a measurable aetheric response
3. That the data can be correlated with material changes and fMRI, as measured by a competent psychological medical researcher, over a series of months as practice improves results
4. That the White Space is the individual encountering direct connection to the Aether.
5. That either could be a MIMS or anti-MIMS, and these should be carefully measured and compared with controls and where possible blinding.

There are no, as of yet, hard conclusions. More or less the conclusions are that we need more data, and more effort from the meditation, religious, psychiatric, and medical communities to solve these mysteries as they might actually be truly important not only for the individual but also for all of society. Consider the rates of crime, depression, anxiety, and children's futures, etc... these are the kinds of issues which are easily overlooked as connected, given that mediation is *free*, but also because actually it will be pretty important if it has tremendous leverage⁵⁴ for humanity's future. Not only for our enlightenment, but our very survival and connectedness in a grander framework of energy and life. Isn't that quite the very purpose of any mimsical quest?

⁵⁴ As are the author's and alchemists' experiences of the past.

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